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Position Paper: Should abortion be illegal or legal?

Introduction

Abortion is one of the most debated and controversial issues in modern society. It raises difficult questions about life, rights, and personal autonomy. People have been arguing over this idea: at what stage does life begin in a fetus? Is it at conception, implantation, brain function, or viability? Does bodily autonomy outweigh the right to life? Does a woman have the right to choose what happens to her body, even if it means ending a potential life? All these questions arise when debating whether or not abortion should be illegal. Some people believe abortion should be illegal because it ends a “human life”. Others argue that it should remain legal because individuals have the right to their own personal autonomy and rights to their own body; even if it means terminating a fetus. These opposing views are usually shaped by moral beliefs, religion, law, and personal experiences. In my paper, I will examine with my own personal beliefs and ideas, whether abortion should be illegal by looking at ethical arguments, laws and amendments, and people's personal experiences.

My Position:

1. Violates the 9th amendment.

After doing proper research on this topic, based on ethical and legal considerations, my position is that abortion should be legal. Based on science, ethics, and legal aspects, this seems as though the most, in my own opinion, factually proven side of the argument. I choose my own perspective on arguments solely based on personal experience, second hand accounts and experiences of others, and scientific evidence. To begin, we all have a right to do what we want with our own bodies. Making abortion illegal clearly violates our personal autonomy. Having a law that does not allow us to make a choice of our own body directly goes against the 9th amendment: "The enumeration in the Constitution, of certain rights, shall not be construed to deny or disparage others retained by the people". Basically, this states that no matter what, every person in the United States has the right to their own personal autonomy, and that means the right to terminate a fetus when it is unwanted or harmful to a person. Having a law directly violates our own rights. America was founded on the idea of "inalienable rights", and it even states so in the constitution itself. Taking away the right to abortion would directly violate this amendment. In summary, a woman has the right to make choices for her own body on the basis of the 9th amendment, and a man saying that we cannot do that is simply absurd and against everything America was founded on.

2. Pregnancy causes risks, abortions can save lives.

Pregnancy is a dangerous procedure, it can involve serious risks to both the woman and the baby that could cost them their lives. With access to legal abortions, it allows safe medical care when a

person's health or life is in danger. Abortions are not always a choice, it may be a necessary medical procedure to save the life of a carrying mother. A woman should not be sacrificed for the sake of an unborn child that is not even fully developed. Abortions are sometimes completely necessary to save a living human rather than letting them die for a dead baby. I think that we need to consider the fact that abortions are an actual medical procedure and not just a woman wanting to get rid of an unborn baby. It is not always their choice to get an abortion, but something needed to save their life. Banning abortions may save an embryo, but not the actual life of the woman carrying the baby. It values a dead, unborn, undeveloped embryo over the life of the mother.

3. Babies are not a requirement.

Abortions are a way for women to get rid of babies they don't want or are simply unable to care for. Of course, women can have a baby if they want one, but the option to get rid of one should also be accessible. What happens to the children who are forced to have a child due to rape? Should they be forced to endure the trauma of pregnancy that even grown women have been traumatized from? If a grown woman cannot handle the trauma of pregnancy what expects people to assume a child should have to go through the same process? Most pro-life debaters often argue that it is the fault of the person who got pregnant, and they should have to face the aftermath of their actions. But most commonly, a majority of women who want an abortion are victims of rape. Over 22% of all abortions in 14 states are due to reasons of rape or incest.¹

¹ "The JAMA paper's estimates for rape-related pregnancies, however, when converted to 12-month estimates, imply that about 22 percent of all abortions in these 14 states would have been sought for reasons of rape or incest, if not for the abortion bans."

<https://www.heritage.org/life/commentary/bad-math-bad-research-the-truth-about-abortion-and-rape-related-pregnancy>.

Survivors of the trauma and abuse of rape and incest should not be forced to endure and carry a reminder of the abuse they went through. They should be given the option of getting rid of a pregnancy they did not want or were forced through. Although in most cases they do choose to keep the child, they should still be given the option to keep it or not.

4. Safety of women and mortality.

When abortion is legalized, it reduces the amount of unsafe at home abortions and procedures, leading to less fatalities among pregnant women. When people are in situations like pregnancy, they will often resort to drastic measures to end the lives of babies they don't want. Teens who are scared of their parents finding out, or a mother who simply can't afford a child, these are the kinds of people that are more likely to do these kinds of dangerous at-home abortions, as a desperate attempt to get rid of an unwanted pregnancy. This year, over 39 women have died from illegal abortions. This risk can be reduced if we give women access to safe abortions by making them legal. Making abortion illegal puts the mothers life at risk and increases the likelihood of desperate people who don't want the baby to do these dangerous illegal abortions. We need to understand that people can be desperate – when they are desperate and backed into a corner, they tend to make drastic decisions and don't think about the consequences that could cost them their lives.

5. Faith and beliefs are not the same as basic science.

The most common argument I hear from pro-lifers is that “according to the bible, life begins at conception” or “the bible says that all forms of life are sacred”. To begin, the argument is very

clearly useless and invalid. Mainly because the bible is not based on real science. The bible cannot be evidence to real, factual, scientific facts. The bible is a faith we constructed ourselves to give us hope and belief in a higher power. It was made for us to have something to put faith in and to follow principles such as loving everyone unconditionally, being kind, respecting others, forgiving everyone, etc. These are mainly the principles that a majority of religions follow.

Although I respect those beliefs and those who follow religious teachings, it is simply not an accurate scientific source. Saying abortion should be illegal because “the bible said so”, is not a solid argument. Although the bible says life begins at conception, it is not true. Life begins after 5-6 weeks of pregnancy, when the fetus begins to develop a heartbeat.² This means that the fetus is not alive, nor breathing, nor moving, at the first 5 weeks. This already disproves what is stated in the bible, and can prove how arguments with the bible saying that abortion should be illegal, are simply just not factually correct. Making abortion illegal because “the bible says life begins at conception” is an argument founded solely on beliefs – not real scientific evidence or facts. I think, making a necessary medical procedure that a woman has a right to choose if she wants or not illegal because “the bible said this” – not based off real factual evidence but someone's beliefs , is simply absurd.

² “One of the milestones of fetal development is when the heart begins to beat. Usually, it may be possible to see the first visible sign of the embryo, known as the fetal pole, at roughly 5–6 weeks of pregnancy.” <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/when-does-a-fetus-have-a-heartbeat>. Accessed 14 April 2026.

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